

same λ and pH value. In (1:1) complexes these proportions are constant and in (2:2) complexes (or more polynuclear complexes) these proportions are variable. Data for the system $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})\text{-RH}_2$ are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. COMPOSITION OF COMPLEXES OF $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ AND RH_2 AT HIGHER pH VALUES

$$C_M = C_L = 2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ or } 1.0 \times 10^{-2}; C_M : C_L = 1 : 1$$

pH values	λ (nm)	A_2	A_1	A_2/A_1
5.8-6.0	480	0.550	0.185	2.97
4.5	480	0.297	0.129	2.30
5.8-6.0	540	0.218	0.055	3.78
4.5	540	0.141	0.047	3.00

From the data the composition of the complexes at higher pH-values appears to be (2:2) or more polynuclear. The compound having the composition (1:2) has been isolated in the solid state², but the existence of the *bis*-compound could not be proved in solution.

References

1. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **10**, 113.
2. N. N. GHOSH, A. MUKHERJEE (*nee* BHATTACHARYYA) and A. BHATTACHARYYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 637.
3. B. BUDESINSKY, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1965, **209**, 379.

Infra-red Absorption at two Microns and Electron Spin Resonance Studies on some Coal-Tar Pitches

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IN a previous paper, Walker and Baumbach¹ have drawn attention to the relation between background absorption at 2μ of coaltar pitches and their quinoline insoluble content. The authors concluded that background absorption at 2μ arises from the quinoline insoluble phase of the pitches. The absorption at 2μ was chosen, because Montgomery and Goodspeed² had shown previously that increased background at that wavelength could be correlated with increased compressive strength of electrodes prepared from the pitches. A fact that was recognised, but not taken into account by Walker and Baumbach¹ is the possible electronic absorption by the quinoline soluble portion of the pitch. The

availability of three pitches, with their quinoline soluble and insoluble fractions separated, enabled this possibility to be tested. Further, in this study, some electron spin resonance measurements have been made on the same pitches, and the quinoline soluble as well as the insoluble fractions of three of them.

The experimental procedure in the case of infra-red absorption was the same as previously¹, except that the material was ground to -200 U.S. sieve, and that 0.6 mg in the case of the original pitch (or its quinoline soluble fraction) or 0.15 mg of the quinoline fraction, as the case may be, was mixed with KBr to make a disc of weight 0.3 g. The discs, specially the ones containing the quinoline insoluble fraction, were transferred to the spectrometer immediately after preparation, because it was found that they developed opacity on keeping.

The electron spin resonance measurements were made on a home-built e.s.r. apparatus at a frequency of 9000 Mc/s, using DPPH as a standard. The pitches (0.03 g) were mixed with an equal quantity of silica (chromatographic grade) in order to eliminate any possible skin effect, although in a few cases tested, no evidence of the latter was found. Since oxygen was found to have a suppressing effect on the intensity, the samples were evacuated in high vacuum (10^{-5} mm. Hg.) overnight at room temperature. Since the purpose of the investigation was a study of the relative variation of e.s.r. parameters with the quinoline insoluble content of the pitches, the values obtained are more relative than absolute.

The infra-red spectrogram obtained for a typical pitch is shown in Fig. 1. The considerable absorption at 2μ has been ascribed by Walker¹ to electronic absorption by the quinoline soluble phase. However, since the absorption at 2μ was found to be constant for the three pitches examined, *viz.*, 5, 14 and 16, the absorption at 2μ of the whole pitches was corrected for the absorption by subtracting this constant amount from the total intensity. This procedure also takes care of any residual scattering. The corrected absorption is plotted against the quinoline insoluble content in Fig. 2.

It is seen that the relationship, observed previously, by Walker and Baumbach¹, is confirmed. Pitch 4 and 5, which were the exceptional pitches of the earlier investigation, still remain so. Investigation with the quinoline insoluble portion of pitches 14 and 16 (Table 1) shows that even in the quinoline insoluble portion, the absorption at 2μ is constant. This result is surprising in view of the opinion prevailing³ that there is a distribution of molecular weight in the quinoline insoluble fraction. Although the present evidence is by no means exhaustive, so far as background absorption is concerned, the quinoline insoluble fractions of normal pitches behave more or less identically.

The results of the present investigation, therefore, have added support to the previous conclusion that

NOTES

Fig. 1

with pitches normally encountered in practice, back-ground absorption at 2μ serves as a good criterion of their insoluble content, and consequently, of the compressive strengths of electrodes made from these pitches.

are higher (it is very difficult to make any statements of a more quantitative nature on these pitches on account of the labile nature of these materials) than those of the original pitches. There is one difference,

TABLE 1. BACKGROUND ABSORPTION AT 2μ OF QUINOLINE INSOLUBLE FRACTION OF PITCHES

Pitch	% Quinoline Insoluble	Back-ground Absorption $\log(I_0/I_b)$
BD-PSU 16	4.9	1.07
BD-PSU 14	17.9	1.07
BD-PSU 5	8.6	0.77*

* 0.6 mg of material. I_b is the intensity of the background (as % transmission at 2μ).

The spin concentrations, line widths and g -values obtained for the samples in e.s.r. measurements, are given in Table 2. It is seen that there is a general increase in spin concentration with increase in the quinoline insoluble content of the pitches, although the relationship is not linear, and pitches 1 and 4 form notable exceptions. The behaviour of pitch 4 (made by adding thermax to tar) is not surprising, as it is not a normal pitch and behaved abnormally in the infra-red study also. However, the result with pitch 1 is rather unexpected.

An interesting point is the more or less equal spin concentration of the quinoline soluble portions of pitches 5, 14 and 16. This recalls the observation made previously, in the infra-red study of these pitch fractions, that the back-ground absorption at 2μ is the same in all the three quinoline soluble fractions. Again, as seen previously with background absorption at 2μ , the spin concentrations of the quinoline insoluble portions of pitches 14 and 16

TABLE 2. SPIN CONCENTRATION, LINE-WIDTH AND g -VALUES OF COAL-TAR PITCHES, AND THE QUINOLINE SOLUBLE AND INSOLUBLE FRACTIONS OF THREE OF THESE PITCHES

Pitch	% Quinoline Insoluble	Spin Concentration $\times 10^{-18}/g$	Line Width Gauss	g -value*
BD-PSU-16	5.2	0.9	3.5	2.0023
BD-PSU- 2	5.7	1.4	4.9	2.0023
BD-PSU- 5	8.6	2.4	6.3	2.0024
BD-PSU-11	8.8	8.4	4.2	2.0026
BD-PSU- 8	10.2	10.2	—	—
BD-PSU- 6	13.0	17.7	3.5	2.0014
BD-PSU- 1	15.8	7.7	3.8	2.0017
BD-PSU-14	17.0	20.0	4.2	2.0016
BD-PSU- 4	13.4	0.4	6.3	2.0022
<i>Quinoline Soluble Fractions</i>				
BD-PSU- 5		2.4	8.2	2.0024
BD-PSU-14		2.8	7.1	2.0022
BD-PSU-16		2.8	6.6	2.0022
<i>Quinoline Insoluble Fractions</i>				
BD-PSU- 5		2.8	7.0	2.0026
BD-PSU-14		23.0	3.1	2.0026
BD-PSU-16		14.0	3.1	2.0024

* The g -values in some cases are lower than the free spin value. This is probably due to experimental errors.

however, between the results of the infra-red study and the e.s.r. one. Whilst the background absorption at 2μ was almost the same in all the pitches, a difference is noticeable in the spin concentrations,

Fig. 2

the quinoline insoluble fraction of pitch 14 revealing a larger number of spins than the corresponding fraction from pitch 16. The similarity in infra-red and e.s.r. behaviour is carried one step further by the fact that the quinoline insoluble fraction of pitch 5 (a lignite pitch) has an abnormally low spin concentration as compared to the corresponding fractions from the other two pitches. In the infra-red study also, the quinoline insoluble fraction of pitch 5 showed an abnormally low background absorption at 2μ .

A similar demarcation is possible when the line widths are compared of the unfiltered pitches and their quinoline soluble and insoluble fractions, the line widths being higher in the case of the quinoline soluble fractions, and smaller with the quinoline insoluble fractions than with the corresponding unfiltered pitches. The only differences is that whereas with the unfiltered pitches, the spin concentration increased with increase in the quinoline insoluble content, no such relationship is noticeable with the line width. Pitch 5, as also its quinoline insoluble fraction, forms an exception even here.

The g -values, however, show no trend.

The close similarity between the electron spin resonance and the infra-red behaviour of the pitches throws light on the nature of the free radical species in pitches. Walker and Baumbach¹ have suggested previously that background absorption at 2μ originates from the electrons in pitches. Following Ingram⁴, these mobile electrons stabilised by aromatic ring clusters seem to be responsible for the free radical behaviour of the pitches. The narrowing of line-width at high free radical concentration, as also the oxygen effect mentioned above, is in line with the above explanation.

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References

1. WALKER and BAUMBACH, Proc. of the Fifth Carbon Conference, Pergamon Press, N.Y., 1963, p. 175.
2. GOODSPEED and MONTGOMERY, Dept. of Mines and Technical Surveys, Ottawa, Report F.R.L. 1956, p. 213.
3. FRANC, *Brennstoff Chemie*, 1956, **36**, 12.
4. INGRAM, Free Radicals as Studied by Electron Spin Resonance, Butterworth, London, 1958, p. 213.

Studies on Hydroxofluoromolybdates (V) of the Type $[\text{Mo}(\text{OH})\text{F}_6]^{2-}$

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STUDIES on the fluoro or oxofluoromolybdates (V) are very scanty. Three such series of anionic complexes, viz., $[\text{MoF}_8]^{3-}$, $[\text{MoF}_6]^-$ and $[\text{MoOF}_5]^{2-}$ have been reported¹. These compounds have been mostly prepared from nonaqueous medium. We are presenting here the isolation of salts of a new series of hydroxofluoromolybdates (V), viz., $M_2[\text{Mo}(\text{OH})\text{F}_6]$ (where $M = \text{K}, \text{Rb}, \text{Cs}, \text{Tl}, \frac{1}{2}\text{N}_2\text{H}_6$ and $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}$) from aqueous solution. The salts have been characterised by elemental analysis, determination of oxidation number of molybdenum, magnetic susceptibility measurement and i.r. spectral studies.

Experimental and Discussion

The parent compound of this series, $\text{N}_2\text{H}_6[\text{Mo}(\text{OH})\text{F}_6]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained by reducing a solution of MoO_3 in 40% HF at water bath temperature with hydrazine (80%) neutralised with the same acid.